

Synthesis and voltammetric behaviour of some biologically active imines

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Abstract : A series of 4-{{(4-phenyl)imino}methyl}-2-methoxyphenols were synthesized and the chemical structure of these compounds were confirmed by elemental and spectral analysis. The voltammetric behaviour of all synthesized compounds was studied on DME and HMDE using differential pulse polarography, cyclic voltammetry and coulometry techniques. The data revealed that the electrode process is irreversible and diffusion controlled. The kinetic parameters, i.e. charge transfer coefficient (αn_a), formation constant ($k^{\circ}_{f,h}$) and diffusion coefficient were also calculated.

Keywords : Imines, differential pulse polarography, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

Imine linkage characterized by $-N=CH-$ is responsible for the biological activity in the compounds¹⁻⁸. Several derivatives constituting azomethine linkage with hydroxy and methoxy substitutions have been reported to show significant biological activities^{9,10}. Imines exhibit a broad spectrum of pharmacological and biological properties such as antimicrobial, analgesic, anticancerous and anti-inflammatory etc. In literature it has been reported that compounds having imine linkage with hydroxy and methoxy substitutions have significant biological activity¹¹⁻¹⁵. Electrochemical behaviour of imines drew the attention of many coworkers¹⁶⁻¹⁹. Fry and Reed²⁰ investigated the reduction mechanism of various imines in DMF using polarography, cyclic voltammetry, coulometry and preparative scale electrolysis. Half wave potential of various imines of the type $ArCH=NAr$ have been compiled by Scott and Jura²¹. Martinet *et al.*²² supported Scott and Jura data in their studies on imines in non-aqueous media. Andrieux *et al.*²³ studied cyclic voltammetric behaviour of various imines and claimed two electron transfer leading to a dimerized product depending on the compound and solvent employed. Unver *et al.*^{24,25} reported the electrochemical study of 1-{{(3-halophenyl)imino}methyl}-2-naphthol and derivatives on graphite electrode, and proposed mechanism for irreversible electrode pro-

cess. The reduction potential of various imines was stated to be dependent on the size of aromatic group at either side of the $C=N$ group²⁶, the type of substituent attached to the aromatic ring²⁷⁻²⁹ and intramolecular hydrogen bonds^{30,31}. Looking to the importance of imines in the present study we synthesized 4-{{(4-phenyl)imino}methyl}-2-methoxyphenols (**3a-d**) and studied the electrochemical behaviour of synthesized compounds.

Results and discussion

The route followed for the synthesis of 4-{{(4-phenyl)imino}methyl}-2-methoxyphenols (**3a-d**) in the laboratory was based on the condensation of aldehyde (**1**) and primary aromatic amines (**2a-d**) (Scheme 1). The products were obtained in 85-90% yields (Table 1).

Differential pulse polarography :

All the synthesized compounds (**3a-d**) gave a single

Table 1. Characteristics of 4-{{(4-substitutedphenyl)imino}methyl}-2-methoxyphenols

Sl. no.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular formula ^a	
3a	-H	174	83.4	$C_{14}H_{13}NO_2$
3b	-F	108	78.5	$C_{14}H_{12}FNO_2$
3c	-Cl	110	86.4	$C_{14}H_{12}ClNO_2$
3d	-Br	115	83.6	$C_{14}H_{12}BrNO_2$

^aAll compounds give consistent C, H and N analysis.

Scheme 1

reduction wave at dropping mercury electrode in the pH range 2.5 to 10.0 due to the reduction of CH=N group (Fig. 1). The peak potential shifted towards more negative potential with the rise in pH for all the compounds indicating the participation of protons in electrode process (Fig. 2). Plots of i_d vs pulse amplitude (Fig. 3) and i_d vs concentration (Fig. 4) are linear passing through the origin confirming the diffusion controlled nature³²⁻³⁵ of the electrode process. The reversibility^{36,37} of the electrode process was established by recording polarograms at different concentrations of the 4-[[4-(4-phenyl)imino]-methyl]-2-methoxyphenols and it was observed that $-E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential with rise in concentration. This behaviour clearly indicates towards irreversible nature^{38,39} of the electrode process, which is further confirmed by logarithmic analysis i.e. the slope of the plot of $[-E_{d.e.} \text{ vs } \log (i/i_d - i) - 0.546 \log t]$ is greater than $59.2/n$ mV, here t is drop time (Fig. 5).

The number of protons (p) involved in the rate determining step is calculated from the slope of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH plot using the following expression :

$$\frac{\partial E_{1/2}}{\partial \text{pH}} = \frac{0.0591}{\alpha n_a} \quad (i)$$

Diffusion coefficient ($D_o^{1/2}$) and heterogenous rate constant ($K_{f,h}^o$) values were calculated from following expression :

$$i_{1/2} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.0591}{\alpha n_a} \cdot \log \frac{1.34 K_{f,h}^o t^{1/2}}{D_o^{1/2}} \quad (ii)$$

Differential pulse polarographic characteristics have been given in Table 2.

Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammetry was performed at hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) in the pH range 2.5-10.0 and exhibited a single cathodic peak assignable to the reduction of CH=N group (Fig. 6). In this pH range no anodic peak could be realized indicating the irreversible nature of the electrode process. Voltammogram were recorded at various scan rates ranging from 100 to 750 mV/s. The cathodic peak potential shifted towards more negative potentials with increasing scan rate as expected for irreversible electron transfer. The plots of i_{pc} (cathodic peak current) vs $\nu^{1/2}$ (scan rate) is a straight line passing through the origin, indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process (Fig. 7). The cathodic peak current increases linearly with the concentration of the depolarizer and hence obeys Randles-Sevcik equation, which implies that the process is diffusion controlled.

Controlled potential electrolysis and coulometry :

By using controlled potential coulometry, the number of electrons transferred, ' n ' were calculated from the charge consumed by the desired concentration of 4-[[4-(4-phenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenols. The charge consumed was determined in acidic medium. For this pur-

Fig. 1. A typical differential pulse polarogram of 4-[[[(4-phenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenol at pH 2.5 and concn $4 \times 10^{-3} M$

Fig. 2. Plots of peak potential vs pH for (A) 4-[[[(4-phenyl)imino]methyl]-, (B) 4-[[[(4-fluorophenyl)imino]methyl]-, (C) 4-[[[(4-chlorophenyl)imino]methyl]-, (D) 4-[[[(4-bromophenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenols at concn $2 \times 10^{-3} M$

Fig. 3. Plots of i_d vs pulse amplitude of (A) 4-[[[(4-phenyl)imino]methyl]-, (B) 4-[[[(4-fluorophenyl)imino]methyl]-, (C) 4-[[[(4-chlorophenyl)imino]methyl]-, (D) 4-[[[(4-bromophenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenols at pH 2.5 and concn $2 \times 10^{-3} M$

pose 2 mL of $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of the electroactive species was placed in the cell and electrolysis was carried

out at $-1.4 V$ against Ag/AgCl reference electrode. During the electrolysis, solution were continuously stirred

Fig. 4. Plots of i_d vs concentration of (A) 4-[[[(4-phenyl)imino]methyl]-, (B) 4-[[[(4-fluorophenyl)imino]methyl]-, (C) 4-[[[(4-chlorophenyl)imino]methyl]-, (D) 4-[[[(4-bromophenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenols at pH 2.5, pulse amplitude 100 mV/s.

Fig. 5. Plot of $-E_{d,c}$ vs $[\log i/i_d - i] - 0.546 \log t$ of 4-[[[(4-phenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenol.

Table 2. Differential pulse polarographic characteristics of 4-[[[(4-substitutedphenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenols
Concentration $4 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH 2.5

Sl. no.	R	$-E_p$ (V)	i_d (μA)	αn_a	I	$\frac{\partial E_{1/2}}{\partial pH}$, V/pH	$D_0^{1/2}$, $\times 10^{-4}$ ($cm^2 s^{-1}$)	$K_{f,h}^0$ ($cm s^{-1}$)
3a	-H	1.27	6.47	1.43	0.49	0.0413	4.0	1.0×10^{-8}
3b	-F	1.26	4.17	1.42	0.31	0.0416	2.6	4.3×10^{-5}
3c	-Cl	1.53	4.22	1.71	0.32	0.0344	2.6	1.8×10^{-9}
3d	-Br	1.39	5.13	1.63	0.38	0.0362	3.2	4.2×10^{-8}

and purged with nitrogen. Number of electrons n was calculated using the equation $Q = nFN$, where Q is the charge in coulombs, F is Faraday constant, and N is the number of moles of the substrate. Disappearance of cathodic

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammograms of 4-[[[(4-fluorophenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenol at different scan rates, pH 6.4, concn. $0.5 \times 10^{-5} M$, pH 2.5.

Fig. 7. Plot of i_d vs v of 4-[[[(4-fluorophenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenol at pH 6.4, concn. $0.5 \times 10^{-5} M$.

peak confirmed reduction of C=N bond. Before and after electrolysis the product was analysed by IR spectroscopy.

Reduction mechanism :

Depending on the forgoing facts and structural genesis of the investigated compounds, the reduction mechanism of 4-[[[(4-phenyl)imino]methyl]-2-methoxyphenols has been postulated. As evidenced from the coulometric studies the number of electrons involved in the reduction are 2 and therefore, it can be proposed that the reduction of imines follows a well defined two step irreversible two electron reduction.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open glass capillary and are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was ascertained by TLC on silica gel plates and spots were visualized using iodine vapours. Elemental analysis was carried out on Carlo Erba 1108 analyser. The IR spectra were recorded using KBr pellets on a Shimadzu, Japan, model Prestize IR 20 spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX 300 (300 MHz, FT NMR) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ using TMS as internal reference.

General procedure for synthesis of compounds :

4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.761 g; 0.005 M) and aniline (0.0465 g; 0.005 M) were dissolved in absolute ethanol and the contents were refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice water and a drop of sulphuric acid was added. The contents were scratched, when solid separated. It was filtered under suction, washed and recrystallized from ethyl alcohol. The colour of synthesized compound 4-((4-phenyl)imino)methyl-2-

methoxyphenol (**3a**) was light brown crystals, m.p. 172 °C, yield 72% (Found : C, 73.47; H, 5.34; N, 6.12. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2$: C, 73.99; H, 5.77; N, 6.16%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1621.55 (-CH=N-), 2933.27 (-OH), 1269.62 and 1018.45 (-OCH₃); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ , ppm : 9.4 (1H, s, -OH), 8.7 (1H, s, -CH=N), 7.2-7.5 (8H, m, Ar-H), 3.2 (3H, s, -OCH₃). Similarly other 4-((4-substitutedphenyl)imino)methyl-2-methoxyphenols (**3b-d**) were synthesized.

Reagents and material :

All the chemicals were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co., Germany. KCl (1.0 mol L⁻¹) solution was prepared in distilled water and used as supporting electrolyte. Stock solutions of synthesized 4-((4-phenyl)imino)methyl-2-methoxyphenols were prepared in ethanol. Solutions for recording voltammograms were prepared by mixing appropriate volume of stock solution and buffer of varying pH. A series of Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 11.0 were prepared. Readymade

precoated TLC silica gel plates from E. Merck, Germany were used for TLC separation. The pH of the buffer was checked using a pH meter (Decible DB-1011 digital pH meter) with a combine glass calomel electrode.

Apparatus :

The differential pulse polarographic (DPP) measurements were carried out using the ELICO CL362 polarographic analyzer (India). The drop time of 1 s was electronically controlled using a 663 VA Stand from the company. The polarograms were recorded using a potential rate of 100 mV s⁻¹. A three-electrode system composed of a dropping mercury electrode (DME), saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode were used. The solutions were purged with pure nitrogen gas for 10 min and then polarographed at ambient temperature. The voltammetry experiments were performed using a Autolab type II (Eco-Chemie B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands) potentiostat-galvanostat with 757 VA computrace software. The utilized electrodes were hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and a graphite rod as auxiliary electrode. The electrochemical cell was Metrohm 663 VA stand. Controlled potential electrolysis experiments were performed using an Autolab Potentiostat/Galvanostat PGSTAT Metrohm 663 VA stand as electrochemical cell, fitted with a PC provided the appropriate GPES 4.2 (General Purpose Electrochemical Software). Coulometric experiments were performed in the potentiostatic mode using Pt foil with large surface area as working electrode and a Pt wire, counter electrode.

Procedure :

The differential pulse polarographic studies were carried out using 2.0 mL stock solution of depolarizer, 1.0 mL of 1 M KCl and 7.0 mL of appropriate buffer. The influence of several buffers (Phosphate, Britton-Robinson and acetate buffer) on the analytical signals was also studied and it is found that the reduction peaks are well defined in BR buffer, so Britton-Robinson buffers were used for maintaining pH. For cyclic voltammetric study, 0.02 M stock solution of depolarizer, 6.0 mL of BR buffer (pH

6.4), 1.0 mL of 1 M KCl and 3 mL of organic solvent (ethanol) were used.

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